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Recent Features and Applications Developed in WEC-Sim for Marine Renewable Energy Research

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Abstract

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) is an open-source software for simulating wave energy converters that has been actively developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Sandia National Laboratories. It has been used to simulate a wide variety of WECs and has gained popularity since its initial release in 2014. WEC-Sim is developed within the MATLAB/SIMULINK environment, which allows users to incorporate different MATLAB packages that are relevant to the renewable energy research community. WEC-Sim is used to perform simulations in the time domain based on the radiation and diffraction method, which uses hydrodynamic coefficients calculated with boundary element method (BEM) frequency-domain potential flow solvers such as WAMIT, NEMOH, Capytaine, or ANSYS-AQWA. Among different applications, WEC-Sim can handle floating body hydrodynamics, mechanical and electrical power generation from WECs, advanced control implementation, mooring systems, and other applications such as desalination. This document aims to highlight the most recent development efforts and applications in WEC-Sim, including the possibility of simulating floating wind turbines, and the improvements on the open-source BEM code Capytaine.

Keywords: Wave energy converter; hydrodynamics modeling; WEC-Sim; offshore wind

1. Introduction

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) is an open-source software tool to simulate wave energy converters in operational waves. WEC-Sim calculates the dynamic interaction between the waves and the floating bodies by solving the time-domain equation of motion based on Cummins formulation [1]:

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$$m\ddot{x}(t) = F_{hs}(t) + F_{ext}(t) + F_{rad}(t) + F_v(t) + F_{PTO}(t) + F_m(t) + F_{nh}(t) \quad (1)$$

A summary of the calculation methods for all the forces from equation (1) is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of calculation methods for the hydrodynamic and external forcing terms.

Forcing Term	Condition	Theory
Radiation (F_{rad})	Regular Waves	Sinusoidal Steady-State Response $F_{rad} = -A(\omega)\ddot{X} - B(\omega)\dot{X}$
	Irregular Waves	Cummins Equation (Convolution Integral) $F_{rad} = -A_{\infty}\ddot{X} - \int_0^t K_r(t-\tau)\dot{X}(\tau)d\tau$
		State Space $\dot{X}_r(t) = A_r X_r(t) + B_r u(t); \int_0^t K_r(t-\tau)u(\tau)d\tau \approx C_r X_r(t) + D_r u(t)$
Wave Excitation (F_{exc})	Regular Waves	Sinusoidal Steady-State Response $F_{exc}(t) = R \left[R_f(t) \frac{H}{2} F_{exc}(\omega, \theta) e^{i\omega t} \right]$
	Irregular Waves	Wave Spectrum $F_{exc}(t) = R \left[R_f(t) \sum_{j=1}^N F_{exc}(\omega_j, \theta) e^{i(\omega_j t + \phi_j)} \sqrt{2S(\omega_j)} d\omega_j \right]$
		Wave Elevation (Convolution Integral) $F_{exc}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_e(t-\tau)\eta(\tau)d\tau$
Hydrostatic restoring force (F_{hs})		Calculated as the product of the hydrostatic stiffness matrix and a vector of displacement: $F_{hs}(t) = K_{hs}X(t)$
PTO (F_{PTO})		Linear spring-Damper $F_{PTO} = -K_{PTO}X_{rel} - C_{PTO}\dot{X}_{rel} \quad P_{PTO} = C_{PTO}\dot{X}_{rel}^2$
		Hydraulic PTO $F_{PTO} = f(X_{rel}, \dot{X}_{rel}, \ddot{X}_{rel}, \dots)$
		Mechanical PTO $P_{PTO} = -F_{PTO}\dot{X}_{rel}$
Mooring (F_m)		Linear Mooring Matrix (i.e., stiffness, damping and pretension)
		Lumped-Mass Mooring Dynamics Model (MoorDyn)
Viscous Force (F_v)		Linear & Quadratic Damping Forces $F_v = -C_v\dot{X} - \frac{C_d\rho A_d}{2} \dot{X} \dot{X} $
		Morison Elements $F_{me} = \rho V \dot{v} + \rho V C_d (\dot{v} - \dot{X}) + \frac{C_d \rho A_d}{2} (v - \dot{X}) v - \dot{X} $
Nonlinear Hydrodynamic Forces (F_{nh})	Nonlinear Hydrodynamics	The additional term accounts for the difference between the nonlinear and linear hydrodynamic forces (buoyancy and the Froude-Krylov force components).

The hydrostatic restoring force, F_{hs} , and the radiation force, F_{rad} , are determined based on the hydrodynamic coefficients calculated from a boundary element method (BEM) software such as Capytaine. The elements of K_{hs} for hydrostatic restoring force, F_{hs} , are defined based on the BEM results. The radiation force is calculated based on the added mass A_{∞} and the radiation impulse function K_r , which are also based on the BEM results.

The BEM results have a huge impact on the numerical models developed in WEC-Sim. Having reliable BEM results is crucial to produce theoretically accurate simulation results. The BEM simulation results are provided as an external input from the user for the WEC-Sim model. The user can use the BEM solver of their preference from a variety of available commercial and open-source options. Capytaine is one of the available open-source codes to calculate BEM coefficients. Capytaine is written in Python with a Fortran core, based on the open linear potential flow solver Nemoh [2] from École Centrale de Nantes. The WEC-Sim Modelling Project at NREL and Sandia Labs is currently funding the development and maintenance of Capytaine [3] to improve open-source toolchains for the numerical modeling and simulation of WECs. The most recent developments on Capytaine are summarized in Section 2 of this document.

One of the most recent features that will be implemented within WEC-Sim is the possibility of simulating floating offshore wind turbines. The Politecnico di Torino has developed MOST (acronym for Matlab for Offshore wind turbine Simulation Tool) which is a Simscape library that offers additional Simulink blocks for the simulation of a floating wind turbine. The most recent efforts on integrating MOST with WEC-Sim are summarized in Section 3 of this document. In addition to the efforts on improving the BEM capabilities of Capytaine and the possibility of simulating offshore wind turbines, the WEC-Sim team is also working on new features based on the input received by the users through the GitHub issues and project board. The future development goals for WEC-Sim are described in Section 4.

2. Capytaine Development

The design of offshore marine devices (such as a wave energy converter or floating wind turbine) requires the interaction of the device and the ocean waves. The most widespread technique is the use of hydrodynamic coefficients computed with a linear potential flow model using a BEM code. Many software packages are available for this task, most of them commercial, such as WAMIT or ANSYS-AQWA. There are fewer free and open-source software (FOSS) options; these often do not have as many features and are generally less accurate than the commercial codes. In order to improve open-source modeling toolchains, the WEC Modelling Project team at NREL and Sandia is currently funding the development of the open-source linear potential flow BEM solver Capytaine [3].

Capytaine is a Python package with a Fortran core, based on the open-source BEM solver Nemoh [2] from École Centrale de Nantes. Development started in 2017 at University College Dublin with the support of MaREI, and version 1.0 was released in 2019 on GitHub (<https://github.com/capytaine/capytaine>). Since the beginning of the new funding by NREL and Sandia in April 2022, five new versions have been released, ~60 issues have been closed, and ~130 pull requests have been merged on GitHub.

The highest priority task of the current development of Capytaine is the improvement of the precision and the performance of the core features of the code, i.e., the resolution of the radiation/diffraction problems. Precision issues in high frequencies had been reported, for instance in [4], causing jumps in the computed hydrodynamical coefficients as illustrated in Fig. 1. The origin of this issue has been tracked down to the computation of the Green function for panels deeper than ~ 1.2 wavelengths (which is most panels at high frequencies), which has been fixed in the latest version. Meanwhile, performance has been improved as shown in Table 2. The performance loss between v1.3 and v1.4 is due to the replacement of the Generalized Minimal Residual Method (GMRES) linear solver by a more robust direct solver. The performance gains in later versions are due to the caching of the lower-upper (LU) decomposition of the direct solver and the fix of a performance bug in the evaluation of the Green function.

Fig. 1. Added mass as a function of the angular frequency for the DeepCWind platform design, computed with two versions of Capytaine. Preposterous results for high frequencies in older versions of Capytaine have been fixed in the latest version.

Another high-priority goal for the future of Capytaine is ensuring its distribution on several platforms and its long-term preservation. For the latest release version, the build and packaging toolchain has been updated to follow the recent changes in the Python packaging ecosystem and to offer more installation options to users. Finally, new features are under development. Hydrostatics have been added in version 1.4 of Capytaine, and in 2.0 their export to WEC-SIM has been streamlined. A prototype of the approximate forward speed by Donatini et al. [5], direct boundary integral equations ("source and dipole" method), as well as irregular frequencies removal techniques are being merged into the code to improve the accuracy and add new features.

Table 2. Resolution time for a 705-panel rectangular barge with 6 degrees of freedom, 2 wave directions, and 20 frequencies, computed with a single core of a high-end CPU from 2017 (Intel Core i7-8700). All tests were run with default settings. (*) Since Nemoh v3 default settings corresponds to higher-accuracy-higher-cost settings, comparison might be biased.

Solver	Release date	Resolution time (infinite depth)	Resolution time (finite depth)
Capytaine v1.3	October 2021	4.9 s	13.1 s
Capytaine v1.4	July 2022	6.5 s	14.1 s
Capytaine v1.5	December 2022	3.7 s	11.1 s
Capytaine v2.0	June 2023	2.3 s	5.5 s
Nemoh v2	May 2016	36 s	56 s
Nemoh v3.0 (*)	December 2022	6 s	20 s

3. MOST: Matlab for Offshore wind turbine Simulation Tool

MOST, which stands for Matlab for Offshore wind turbine Simulation Tool, is a specialized Simscape library designed by the Politecnico di Torino to enhance Simulink's capabilities for simulating floating wind turbines. Integrated within the WEC-Sim environment, MOST offers a range of supplementary Simulink blocks to facilitate the simulation process [6]. One of the key strengths of MOST lies in its seamless integration of multibody dynamics. Leveraging the combined functionalities of MOST and WEC-Sim, it becomes feasible to simulate various scenarios, such as wave energy converters (WECs) integrated with wind turbine platforms or pendulum-type platforms [7], see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Example of hybrid concepts a) of a semisubmersible-pendulum platform and b) of a platform with integrated WEC [7].

The supplementary blocks furnished by MOST encompass various aspects. These include the incorporation of aerodynamics, a wind turbine control system based on ROSCO open-source controller, and an additional module for modeling the quasi-static nonlinear mooring system employing the catenary equation. The ROSCO controller was purposefully created for floating offshore wind turbines and quickly became the established open-source standard for numerous projects. It incorporates familiar control strategies utilized in the wind industry, such as tip speed ratio (TSR) tracking for generator torque and gain-scheduled proportional-integral control for blade pitch [8].

The aerodynamic forces are modeled using lookup tables, based on the blade element momentum theory (BEMT). The set of equations of the BEMT are the same as OpenFAST's Aerodyn module and are described in [9]. Flapwise and edgewise loads generated by the distribution of aerodynamic pressure are precomputed for each blade and applied as external forces during the time-domain simulation, at their respective roots. These loads are discretized with respect to the wind speed, rotor speed, and blade pitch. Throughout the simulation, wind speed along the blade span is averaged to compute these loads. Effects of pitch and surge motion are incorporated by combining the wind speed with the blade's velocity relative to the global reference system. The validation of MOST against OpenFAST, see Fig. 3, made in a previous work [6] showcases its capabilities, albeit with a limitation on platform kinematics, focusing on primary degrees of freedom (surge, pitch, heave).

The primary distinction between MOST and OpenFAST lies in their treatment of aerodynamic forces. The use of lookup tables reduces the computational effort, resulting in a speed improvement of 3 to 5 times. This improvement makes MOST particularly well-suited for optimization purposes, as evidenced by previous studies on the optimization of spar [10] and Hexafloat concepts [11].

Fig. 3: Platform pitch and power output comparison between MOST-LUT (Lookup Table) and FAST for the IEA 15 MW reference wind Turbine [6]

The next steps will mainly involve developing the model to be able to deal with all 6 degrees of freedom. The current approach for solving the aerodynamic loads, which employed lookup tables with averaged wind speed, rotor speed and blade pitch, proves insufficiently effective, particularly for the roll motion. For this reason, the complete resolution of the BEM theory has also been implemented in MOST. Specifically, for each blade node the relative velocity with the wind is calculated, including the apparent wind associated with the motion of the rotor, and the aerodynamic problem is solved according to [9] at each time step. As can be seen in Fig. 4 this method leads to results close to those obtained through OpenFAST even for the 6-degree-of-freedom case. Currently, it is more computationally expensive than the OpenFAST model, so a further goal will be to resolve this issue, for example by resorting to lookup tables by considering more parameters during the simulation.

Fig. 4: Platform roll and yaw comparison between MOST-LUT, MOST-BEM and FAST for the IEA 15 MW wind Turbine

However, it's important to note that the current models lack incorporation of important dynamic effects, notably blade flexibility, which can impact blade load cycling. Addressing this limitation by integrating blade aeroelasticity through modal analysis offers a promising avenue for future enhancements. Furthermore, an additional consideration is the potential to introduce wake interaction effects between turbines. This capability could simulate scenarios like wind farms, encompassing shared mooring lines and installation of multiple turbines on a single platform.

4. Future Development Goals

WEC-Sim receives sustained funding from the US Department of Energy Water Power Technologies Office (WPTO), which allows for continuous maintenance and development of the software. The WEC-Sim development team is continuously working on improving the software by adding new features and capabilities. Most of the new features come from user requests through the GitHub issues board. One of the future development goals that is being considered in WEC-Sim is the possibility to follow a double-peaked spectrum like the Ochi-Hubble [12]. This can be done by having two separate wave trains, with different directions and spectrums. The convolution integral is an accurate method of calculating the total wave radiation forces acting on a body in an irregular sea state. However, convolution integrals can be computationally intensive, especially with small time steps and body-to-body interactions. Updates to the convolution integral block plan to incorporate finite impulse response (FIR) filters to implement and calculate the radiation convolution integral based on the radiation damping impulse response functions and velocity in relevant degrees of freedom. The FIR filter decreases the total computational time of a WEC-Sim simulation with two bodies in an irregular sea state and typical time step by 10-20%. FIR filters are programmatically created during Simulink model compilation based on the number of bodies and degrees of freedom.

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